

THE ROLE OF BIG DATA IN TELECOMMUNICATION BUSINESS

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Abstract: this article discusses the general issues of using big data in the practical plane of the commercial activities of companies. The author focuses on the tasks that can be solved using big data in the telecommunications sector. The characteristics of the company's customers are analyzed, which make it possible to judge their potential outflow. The clusters for which the most successful prediction results were obtained were identified.

Keywords: big data, telecommunications, churn, SVM, neural networks.

Аннотация: в данной статье рассматриваются общие вопросы использования больших данных в практической плоскости коммерческой деятельности компаний. Автор акцентирует внимание на задачах, которые можно решить с помощью больших данных в телекоммуникационной сфере. Анализируются характеристики клиентов компании, что позволяет судить об их потенциальном оттоке. Выявлены кластеры, для которых были получены наиболее успешные результаты предсказания.

Ключевые слова: большие данные, телекоммуникации, отток, SVM, нейронные сети.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada kompaniyalarning tijorat faoliyatining amaliy tekisligida katta ma'lumotlardan foydalanishning umumiy masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Muallif telekommunikatsiya sohasida katta ma'lumotlar yordamida hal qilinishi mumkin bo'lgan vazifalarga e'tibor qaratadi. Kompaniya mijozlarining

xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi, bu ularning potentsial chiqib ketishini baholash imkonini beradi. Eng muvaffaqiyatli bashorat natijalari olingan klasterlar aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: katta ma'lumotlar, telekommunikatsiyalar, churn, SVM, neyron tarmoqlar.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the phrase “big data” has become increasingly popular. It is used with or without reason in articles about future marketing opportunities, industry, telecommunications, service and maintenance organizations that collect information about their customers in any way. But, using this term, the authors do not always understand what actually lies behind these words, usually referring to unstructured arrays of some kind of data that companies have. How to process such arrays and, moreover, how to interpret the results of this processing later, are few. Abroad, the analysis and use by corporations of data about their customers is far from a new thing, but this direction has been developed only in recent decades, when companies have the technical capabilities to accumulate, exchange and process large amounts of information. Big data has been widely used in government agencies of the United States, in medicine, the financial sector and telecommunications [1]. The analysis, structuring and subsequent targeted use of information about the citizens of the country and / or about the company's customers allows corporations to save millions of dollars in logistics, personnel costs and profitability.

In Uzbekistan, there is currently a significant gap in the telecommunications market between the large amount of information about the subscriber accumulated over many years and how this information is used within the company. Only a small percentage of the data about its subscribers is taken into account when solving problems that arise, for example, during network planning or during subscriber development.

However, having data on the consumption and payments of the subscriber, its geosocial characteristics, on which places the client visits more often, the range of tasks that Big Data can solve can be considered quite widely.

How specifically mobile operators can use customer data, foreign experience suggests. The first experiments with big data were used in the United States for planning a radio network: based on the current load of base stations, operators drew conclusions about how quickly the population of a particular area was growing, where active development and settlement was taking place, and, based on these data, developed radio frequency network. In the future, interest shifted towards the development of the subscriber: the individuality of the subscriber was put at the forefront of working with big data. With the advent of smartphones, the involvement of the population in social networks, personalization and individualization only intensified, allowing companies, including mobile operators, to work with each client almost individually, sending him targeted offers. There is a known case [2] when one of the retail chains in the United States sent an SMS to its client, a young girl with an advertisement for products for pregnant women. The system of this network made such a conclusion by analyzing the customer's purchases for recent months. The indignant father of the girl considered himself and his, as it seemed to him, innocent daughter offended and sued the network. However, the case was soon closed, because the girl really turned out to be pregnant. This is one of many examples of correct (though not very successful) targeting. Perhaps you yourself noticed that you should visit a site of a certain subject, and the next day you see the corresponding advertisement in browsers and, possibly, receive SMS with the subject of the site that you visited yesterday.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

At the first stage of our research, we set ourselves several relevant commercial tasks:

1. Determination from a sample of subscriber numbers prone to churn.
2. Determination from a sample of numbers of subscribers who are prone to changing the device.

The relevance of the first task is determined by the following: the penetration of cellular communications in Kazakhstan is approaching 200%. This suggests that

for every inhabitant of the country there will soon be at least 2 SIM cards of any mobile operators. This, in turn, means that every year it becomes more and more difficult for operators to attract new subscribers. New connections are more like "grinding" either their own base or competitors' subscribers, who are more sensitive to new price offers. It is clear that attracting a new subscriber is an additional cost for the operator, expressed in commissions. Thus, the task of retaining the "old" or existing subscriber has certain economic grounds.

The relevance of the second task is due to the following: according to the available data of operators, subscribers using smartphones have a higher profitability than subscribers using the so-called feature-phones (regular phones). Basically, this is due to the fact that on smartphones, subscribers have more opportunities to use the mobile Internet. Accordingly, the second task should solve the problem of accelerating the subscriber's transition from a simpler device to a more modern one (smartphone or tablet).

The set of analyzed variables for the two problems should, of course, be different. If in the first case we are more likely to be interested in data on the subscriber's voice consumption in the context of directions and its charges and payments, then in the second case, the indicators of the subscriber's data traffic consumption, the type of his device, the frequency of access to the network and the structure of ARPU (average customer profitability) are more interesting. per month). As already mentioned above, client data, including in the telecommunications environment, have been studied abroad for a long time. Therefore, we turned to the European experience in Ireland and telecommunications operators in Southeast Asia and looked at what Singaporean and Taiwanese telecom operators did with their data [3-5]. In addition, while searching for examples of machine learning, I came across a rather interesting article [6] on the database of one of the Chinese banks. All studies concerned the movement of the client base of these companies and were of great interest to us, since the task of predicting the outflow is also, in essence, the movement of the client base. Machine learning models in these studies included

logistic regression, neural networks, decision trees, random forest and k-means clustering and were considered in these studies in combination with each other. The approach with a combination of learning methods is a completely justified decision by analysts at the stage of machine learning. Yes, the structure of the client base and the field of activity of the companies are similar, but at the time of the start of the research it is not clear which of the methods will work. Since these works eventually identified a set of promising methods that showed the best results for the type of tasks associated with the outflow of the customer base, it was decided in our study to rely on this set of learning methods: “Gradient boosting”, “Random forest”, “Logistic regression and Neural Networks.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM SOLUTION

The problem was solved in two stages. Samples were prepared for both stages: at the training stage, we told the machine the parameters of each client and the result of this client (that is, the client remains in the database or falls into the outflow), and at the testing stage, on the second sample, we made predictions and evaluated the results according to the selected metrics.

The parameters of prediction accuracy (precision) and completeness of prediction (recall) were used as metrics in the study. Simply put, how many of the actual churned customers the model was able to predict and what percentage of accuracy was in the sample of customers that the model considered prone to churn. Another quality indicator that we used to compare classifiers was the AUC metric. At the first stage of training for each method, information about voice traffic, SMS traffic and data traffic in the context of ten call directions was uploaded as initial data. The data was presented on a sample of almost 400,000 subscribers. We took the consumption of these subscribers in the context of 15 months, starting from mid-2013. In addition, the TAC device number (TypeAllocationCode) served as an additional parameter, by which it was possible to set the client device type (smartphone, tablet, simple phone), device manufacturer, operating system, model

year, Wi-Fi support, device specifications (display size) and characteristics of supported network generations (2G/UMTS/LTE).

The test sample did not show significant achievements at the first stage of processing. In fact, there was no understanding of what parameters de facto affect the outflow. Before the start of the study, we had thoughts that the more parameters in the samples we can prepare and load, the higher the accuracy of prediction and estimation will be. However, after the first approach, the opposite assumption arose that there are too many parameters, and they negatively affect learning and prediction. In this regard, we decided to evaluate the importance of the characteristics and see which of them have the greatest impact on the result. During the evaluation, it turned out that the most significant characteristics were the date of registration (in other words, the lifetime of the client in the network), the total number of incoming voice minutes and the amount of data traffic consumed. Among the least influential characteristics were indicators of the type of the client's set and outgoing calls in the direction of long-distance and city numbers. This, in general, lends itself to logic, since in the current realities, landline phones are really losing their popularity, and long-distance calls are more of a one-time necessity than some kind of permanent action, based on which one can draw conclusions about the outflow.

Given the above, we excluded insignificant parameters and supplemented the sample with data on the client's place of residence, gender, age, and legal status (that is, we checked whether the client is an individual or the contract was concluded for a legal entity).

And already with these parameters, the metrics of the test sample began to show results an order of magnitude better. In addition, before one of the next steps in testing the sample, the group proposed to group the parameters. We combined several parameters together and tested on a group of parameters. As a result of sorting through the cluster options, the most successful results were obtained for the section: legal status + gender + lifetime in the network + phone/smartphone user.

We saw that by separating these indicators, we get significant precision and recall indicators, and the AUC was 0.88.

3. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

It turned out that for users of phones with a network lifetime of less than 2 years, the outflow is quite difficult to predict. From a commercial point of view, this can be explained by the fact that a lot of promotions have recently been held with equipment, when a discount on equipment and / or free traffic is provided when buying a device. Therefore, often, along with high-quality connections, the operator recruits low-quality subscribers into the base, who use promotional traffic and do not use the device further. As far as non-tethering device users are concerned, it makes sense that the machine is more accurate and complete in predicting results for customers with a lifespan of more than 2 years, since more complete data allows you to track the seasonality of consumption and identify points of decline in network activity as an indicator that a customer prone to outflow.

For the second task of researching clients prone to changing devices, the data set uploaded for the first task was not enough. We set the TAC change as the trigger. But in a sample of 400 thousand customers, there were only about 25 thousand people who used phones, replacing them later on with smartphones.

4. CONCLUSION

Although not everything turned out perfectly, already the first results satisfied the customers of the study and gave us experience in the practical application of a new interesting area of informatics - machine learning. As is usually the case in research projects, in the process of work, many new interesting problems and proposals for solving them appeared. Without any doubt, research in this area will continue.

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